

Supporting Information

Synergistic Effects in Oxygen Evolution Activity of Mixed Iridium-Ruthenium Pyrochlores

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Figure S1 Results of the Rietveld refinement performed using the Profex 3.13.0 software to determine the content of contamination with primary oxides, exemplary shown for the $\text{Gd}_2(\text{Ru}_{0.17}\text{Ir}_{0.73})_2\text{O}_7$ which showed the highest contamination

$R_{wp}=11.13\%$, $R_{exp}=1.52\%$,
 $\chi^2=53.6171$ GOF=7.3224

Parameter, Goal	Value	ESD
IrO_2	0.0213	0.0018
$\text{Gd}_2(\text{RuIr})_2\text{O}_7$	0.9344	0.005
Gd_2O_3	0.0443	0.0048

Figure S2 SEM micrographs depicting the morphologies of the pyrochlore samples prepared by the spray-freeze freeze-drying approach with subsequent prolonged annealing in air at 1020 °C.

Figure S3 Ir-Ir and Ir-Ru distances as a function of Ru-Ru distance (a) and Ir-Ln and Ru-Ln (Ln=Yb, Gd, Nd) distances (b) as a function of Ru-Ru distance for Yb, Gd, and Nd stabilized pyrochlores featuring coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure as obtained from the fitting of the EXAFS functions. The data were taken from Table S2.

The refined metal-metal distances are compared in **Figure S3**. As follows from **Figure S3** the average distance of Ir-Ir pairs is longer than that of the Ru-Ru pairs. The Ir-Ir distance remains longer than that one of the Ru-Ru pair, regardless of the size of the lanthanide in the A-site. The distances between the A- and B-site cations (M-Ln distances) also show a strong correlation with the Ru-Ru bond lengths (**Figure S3b**). While the Ru-Ln distances correlate with the Ru-Ru distance in a linear fashion (with a slope of one), the Ir-Ln distances show a weaker correlation. In particular, the Yb-Ir distances are significantly longer than the corresponding Ru-Ru, but also Ru-Yb distances. The Nd-Ir and Gd-Ir bonding distances, however, tend to be slightly shorter than the corresponding Ru-Ru, Ru-Nd, and Ru-Gd distances.

Figure S4 Linear sweep voltammograms of ytterbium (a), gadolinium (b), and neodymium (c) pyrochlores of general composition $\text{Ln}_2(\text{Ru}_x\text{Ir}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_7$ measured in acidic media ($v = 10 \text{ mV/s}$). The actual x is shown in the figure legend.

Figure S5 Tafel plots of all mixed pyrochlore catalysts conforming to the composition $\text{Ln}_2(\text{Ru}_x\text{Ir}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_7$ with $\text{Ln} = \text{Yb}, \text{Gd}, \text{Nd}$ constructed from the steady-state chronoamperometric experiments. The curve assignment is listed in the figure legend.

Figure S6 Potential in the RHE scale at a current density of 10 mA/cm^2 obtained from the linear sweep voltammograms of the pyrochlore samples at a polarization rate of 1 mV/s plotted versus the ruthenium content of the respective sample.

Table S1 Particle size distribution from the statistical analysis of at least 400 data points of individual pyrochlore particles as obtained from the SEM pictures.

x(Ru)	Ytterbium [nm]	x(Ru)	Gadolinium [nm]	x(Ru)	Neodymium [nm]
1.00	83±11	1.00	173±12	1.00	350±12
0.70	117±7	0.73	210±42	0.73	327±22
0.58	99±6	0.55	183±18	0.58	288±15
0.45	103±5	0.45	235±10	0.42	335±19
0.15	87±19	0.17	123±9	0.16	323±17
0.00	156±9	0.00	142±5	0.00	348±23

Table S2 Local structure parameters of pyrochlore samples without cation mixing in the B-site obtained in NLLS fits of the Ru K-edge and Ir L_{III}-edge EXAFS functions (k^3 normalized), including the goodness of fit (R-factor), Debye-Waller factors σ , absorption edges E_0 , as well as occupation and refined values of the effective scattering paths. The k-range used in the refinement for the Fourier transform was adjusted for each refined spectrum independently, according to the quality of the measured signal

Yb₂Ru₂O₇ Ru-Edge 19 independent points, 9 variables, R=0.021, $E_0=22115.0\pm 1.3$ eV, k-range 3-14 Å ⁻¹					Yb₂Ir₂O₇ Ir-Edge 20 independent points, 11 variables, R=0.018, $E_0=11226.3\pm 0.9$ eV, k-range 3-14 Å ⁻¹				
scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	0.85±0.05	1	0.002	1.99±0.01	Ir-O	0.82±0.04	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	0.90±0.02	1	0.003	3.58±0.01	Ir-Ir	0.85±0.09	1	0.003	3.60±0.01
Ru-Yb	0.82±0.02	1	0.006	3.58±0.02	Ir-Yb	0.80±0.03	1	0.003	3.53±0.03

Gd₂Ru₂O₇ Ru-Edge 9 independent points, 9 variables, R=0.032, $E_0=22117.3\pm 1.6$ eV, k-range 3-14 Å ⁻¹					Gd₂Ir₂O₇ Ir-Edge 20 independent points, 9 variables, R=0.018, $E_0=11230.2\pm 0.8$ eV, k-range 3-14 Å ⁻¹				
scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	0.84±0.06	1	0.002	1.99±0.01	Ir-O	0.87±0.04	1	0.002	2.03±0.01
Ru-Ru	0.80±0.03	1	0.004	3.60±0.01	Ir-Ir	0.81±0.03	1	0.003	3.64±0.01
Ru-Gd	0.92±0.03	1	0.006	3.60±0.03	Ir-Gd	0.82±0.03	1	0.006	3.60±0.01

Nd₂Ru₂O₇ Ru-Edge 19 independent points, 9 variables, R=0.031, $E_0=22116.1\pm 1.5$ eV, k-range 3-14 Å ⁻¹					Nd₂Ir₂O₇ Ir-Edge 16 independent points, 9 variables, R=0.018, $E_0=11229.6\pm 1.1$ eV, k-range 3-12 Å ⁻¹				
scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	S_0^2	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	0.84±0.06	1	0.003	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	0.87±0.04	1	0.002	2.01±0.01
Ru-Ru	0.74±0.04	1	0.004	3.65±0.01	Ir-Ir	0.85±0.04	1	0.003	3.69±0.01
Ru-Nd	0.92±0.04	1	0.007	3.64±0.03	Ir-Nd	0.78±0.04	1	0.006	3.62±0.01

Table S3 Local structure parameters of pyrochlore samples with cation mixing in the B-site obtained in NLLS fits of the Ru K-edge and Ir L_{III}-edge EXAFS functions (k^3 normalized), including goodness of fit (R-factor), Debye-Waller factors σ , absorption edges E_0 , as well as occupation, refined values of the effective scattering paths, and k-range. The iridium – ruthenium distance was obtained from modeling the data at the iridium edge and then kept constant at the ruthenium edge. The occupancies of ruthenium and iridium in the B-site were calculated assuming normal multiplicity N of the B-site using the amplitude factor S_0^2 obtained from the pyrochlores without cation mixing, listed in Table S2. The occupancy was modeled as a dependent variable using the relation $x(\text{Ru}) = x$ and $x(\text{Ir}) = 1-x$.

Yb₂(Ru_{0.15}Ir_{0.85})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 10 variables, R=0.015,				
E₀=22115.6±1.2 eV, k-range 3-11 Å⁻¹					E₀=11225.1±0.9 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	1.97±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.98±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.30±0.21	0.003	3.58±0.02	Ir-Ir	6	0.76±0.19	0.003	3.61±0.02
Ru-Ir	6	0.70±0.21	0.003	3.64	Ir-Ru	6	0.24±0.19	0.003	3.64±0.04
Ru-Yb	6	1	0.004	3.58±0.03	Ir-Yb	6	1	0.006	3.58±0.04

Yb₂(Ru_{0.45}Ir_{0.55})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 10 variables, R=0.009,				
E₀=22115.9±1.2 eV, k-range 3-14 Å⁻¹					E₀=11226.5±0.7 eV, k-range 3-13 Å⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.45±0.17	0.003	3.59±0.02	Ir-Ir	6	0.45±0.13	0.003	3.62±0.02
Ru-Ir	6	0.55±0.17	0.003	3.59	Ir-Ru	6	0.55±0.13	0.003	3.59±0.01
Ru-Yb	6	1	0.007	3.59±0.04	Ir-Yb	6	1	0.006	3.57±0.02

Yb₂(Ru_{0.58}Ir_{0.42})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					20 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.013,				
E₀=22114.6±1.5 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹					E₀=11225.5±0.5 eV, k-range 3-14 Å⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.54±0.15	0.003	3.57±0.02	Ir-Ir	6	0.39±0.10	0.003	3.61±0.01
Ru-Ir	6	0.46±0.15	0.003	3.58	Ir-Ru	6	0.61±0.10	0.003	3.58±0.01
Ru-Yb	6	1	0.007	3.57±0.03	Ir-Yb	6	1	0.005	3.57±0.01

Yb₂(Ru_{0.70}Ir_{0.30})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					17 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.011,				
E₀=22115.2±1.0 eV, k-range 3-14 Å⁻¹					E₀=11224.1±0.7 eV, k-range 3-13 Å⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.68±0.12	0.003	3.59±0.01	Ir-Ir	6	0.38±0.10	0.003	3.59±0.04
Ru-Ir	6	0.32±0.12	0.003	3.59	Ir-Ru	6	0.62±0.10	0.003	3.59±0.01
Ru-Yb	6	1	0.006	3.59±0.01	Ir-Yb	6	1	0.003	3.59±0.03

Gd₂(Ru_{0.17}Ir_{0.83})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.012,				
16 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.027,					E₀=11224.5±0.8 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
E₀=22115.2±1.2 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹									
Scattering Path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.31±0.11	0.003	3.66±0.01	Ir-Ir	6	0.78±0.20	0.003	3.66±0.01
Ru-Ir	6	0.69±0.11	0.003	3.64	Ir-Ru	6	0.22±0.20	0.003	3.64±0.03
Ru-Gd	6	1	0.006	3.64±0.02	Ir-Gd	6	1	0.006	3.61±0.03

Gd₂(Ru_{0.45}Ir_{0.55})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.016,				
17 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.026,					E₀=11224.7±0.9 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
ΔE₀=22115.1±1.4 eV, k-range 3-13 Å⁻¹									
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.48±0.07	0.003	3.62±0.03	Ir-Ir	6	0.58±0.24	0.003	3.68±0.03
Ru-Ir	6	0.52±0.07	0.003	3.61	Ir-Ru	6	0.42±0.24	0.003	3.61±0.03
Ru-Gd	6	1	0.006	3.64±0.03	Ir-Gd	6	1	0.004	3.59±0.03

Gd₂(Ru_{0.55}Ir_{0.45})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.018,				
18 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.020,					E₀=11224.8±0.9 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
E₀=22115.2±1.4 eV, k-range 3-13 Å⁻¹									
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.003	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.66±0.15	0.003	3.62±0.03	Ir-Ir	6	0.48±0.24	0.003	3.69±0.04
Ru-Ir	6	0.34±0.15	0.003	3.62	Ir-Ru	6	0.52±0.24	0.003	3.62±0.02
Ru-Gd	6	1	0.006	3.64±0.03	Ir-Gd	6	1	0.004	3.59±0.03

Gd₂(Ru_{0.73}Ir_{0.27})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.017,				
16 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.025,					E₀=11224.2±0.8 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
E₀=22115.0±1.6 eV, k-range 3-14 Å⁻¹									
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.003	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.69±0.21	0.003	3.62±0.02	Ir-Ir	6	0.33±0.17	0.003	3.71±0.06
Ru-Ir	6	0.31±0.21	0.003	3.63	Ir-Ru	6	0.67±0.17	0.003	3.63±0.02
Ru-Gd	6	1	0.006	3.61±0.06	Ir-Gd	6	1	0.004	3.62±0.03

Nd₂(Ru_{0.42}Ir_{0.58})₂O₇					Ir-Edge				
Ru-Edge					16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.012,				
18 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.021,					E₀=11224.2±0.7 eV, k-range 3-12 Å⁻¹				
E₀=22114.8±1.2 eV, k-range 3-13 Å⁻¹									
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.003	2.01±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	2.01±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.46±0.11	0.003	3.66±0.01	Ir-Ir	6	0.51±0.17	0.003	3.72±0.03
Ru-Ir	6	0.54±0.11	0.003	3.66	Ir-Ru	6	0.49±0.17	0.003	3.66±0.03
Ru-Nd	6	1	0.006	3.67±0.04	Ir-Nd	6	1	0.004	3.65±0.02

Nd₂(Ru_{0.58}Ir_{0.42})₂O₇ Ru-Edge 16 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.027, E ₀ =22115.7±1.6 eV, k-range 3-12 Å ⁻¹					Ir-Edge 16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.019, E ₀ =11223.9±0.9 eV, k-range 3-12 Å ⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.003	2.01±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	2.00±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.64±0.15	0.003	3.70±0.03	Ir-Ir	6	0.55±0.14	0.003	3.74±0.04
Ru-Ir	6	0.36±0.15	0.003	3.65	Ir-Ru	6	0.45±0.14	0.003	3.65±0.02
Ru-Nd	6	1	0.006	3.73±0.05	Ir-Nd	6	1	0.004	3.65±0.01

Nd₂(Ru_{0.73}Ir_{0.27})₂O₇ Ru-Edge 17 independent points, 7 variables, R=0.030, E ₀ =22115.8±1.7 eV, k-range 3-13 Å ⁻¹					Ir-Edge 16 independent points, 8 variables, R=0.017, E ₀ =11224.1±1.0 eV, k-range 3-12 Å ⁻¹				
scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]	scattering path	N	occ.	σ [Å ²]	bond length [Å]
Ru-O	6	1	0.003	2.00±0.01	Ir-O	6	1	0.002	1.99±0.01
Ru-Ru	6	0.77±0.11	0.003	3.68±0.03	Ir-Ir	6	0.42±0.12	0.003	3.71±0.04
Ru-Ir	6	0.23±0.11	0.003	3.63	Ir-Ru	6	0.58±0.12	0.003	3.63±0.02
Ru-Nd	6	1	0.006	3.70±0.04	Ir-Nd	6	1	0.004	3.62±0.01

Table S4 Surface charge of the pyrochlore samples as calculated from cyclic voltammograms (average integration of anodic and cathodic scans) measured between 1.0 and 1.4 V vs. RHE at a polarization rate of 10 mV/s.

x(Ru)	Ytterbium [mC/cm ²]	x(Ru)	Gadolinium [mC/cm ²]	x(Ru)	Neodymium [mC/cm ²]
0.70	0.19	0.73	0.13	0.73	0.20
0.58	0.18	0.55	0.16	0.58	0.15
0.45	0.17	0.45	0.12	0.42	0.10
0.15	0.14	0.17	0.15	0.16	0.47